

Enhancing Orthodontic Treatment Efficiency Through Periodontally Accelerated Osteogenic Orthodontics (PAOO): A Case Report

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Abstract

Background: Orthodontic space closure in adult patients is often challenging due to reduced bone remodelling capacity, prolonged treatment duration, and increased risk of periodontal complications. Periodontally Accelerated Osteogenic Orthodontics (PAOO) is a surgically assisted orthodontic technique that combines selective alveolar corticotomy with bone grafting to enhance regional acceleratory phenomenon (RAP), thereby facilitating faster and more stable tooth movement.

Case Presentation: A 26 year old female patient presented with spacing in the maxillary left premolar region requiring orthodontic space closure. Considering the patient's age and the need to reduce overall treatment time while maintaining periodontal health, PAOO was planned as an adjunct to fixed orthodontic therapy. Following full thickness flap reflection, selective corticotomy was performed around the involved teeth. Orthodontic force application was initiated two weeks post surgery.

Results: Rapid orthodontic tooth movement was observed with efficient space closure achieved within a significantly reduced treatment period compared to conventional orthodontics. Clinical evaluation revealed satisfactory alignment, stable occlusion, and improved periodontal parameters. Adequate alveolar bone levels with no evidence of root resorption or periodontal breakdown during follow-up was noticed.

Conclusion: PAOO technique proved to be an effective and safe adjunctive procedure for accelerated orthodontic space closure in adult patients. This technique has reduced treatment duration, enhanced alveolar bone support, and predictable clinical outcomes, making it a valuable interdisciplinary approach in selected orthodontic cases.

Keywords: Periodontally Accelerated Osteogenic Orthodontics, PAOO, Accelerated Orthodontics, Space Closure, Corticotomy.

Introduction

The demand for orthodontic treatment among adult patients has increased significantly in recent decades due to growing esthetic awareness and advancements in dental care. However, orthodontic treatment in adults presents unique biological and clinical challenges. Reduced cellular activity, increased bone density, and diminished vascularity of the alveolar bone result in slower orthodontic tooth movement compared to adolescents. Consequently, prolonged treatment duration may lead to compromised patient compliance and increased risks of root resorption, periodontal breakdown, and relapse.^{1,2}

In order to overcome these limitations, various techniques have been proposed to accelerate orthodontic tooth movement, including low level laser therapy, vibration devices, pharmacological agents, and surgically assisted orthodontic procedures. Among these

modalities, corticotomy assisted orthodontics has gained considerable attention due to its predictable biological response and clinical effectiveness.³

The concept of corticotomy facilitated tooth movement was first introduced by Köle in 1959, who proposed that selective alveolar decortication could enable rapid movement of blocks of bone containing teeth. Although his technique demonstrated reduced treatment time, it involved extensive surgical intervention and was therefore limited in routine clinical application. Subsequent studies clarified that orthodontic tooth movement following corticotomy occurs primarily through bone remodeling rather than en bloc movement.

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The biological foundation for accelerated tooth movement following surgical injury is explained by the regional acceleratory phenomenon (RAP), a concept described by Frost. RAP refers to a localized, transient increase in bone turnover and remodeling activity in response to noxious stimuli such as surgical trauma. This phenomenon leads to temporary osteopenia, reduced bone density, and increased metabolic activity, thereby facilitating faster orthodontic tooth movement during the healing phase.^{6,7}

Based on these principles, Wilcko and colleagues introduced Periodontally Accelerated Osteogenic Orthodontics (PAOO) in the early 2000s. This technique integrates selective alveolar corticotomy, particulate bone grafting, and conventional orthodontic mechanics to accelerate tooth movement while simultaneously enhancing alveolar bone density.^{8,9} PAOO not only shortens overall treatment time, it also improves periodontal support, reduce the risk of dehiscence and fenestration, and enhance long-term stability.¹⁰

Clinical studies have reported that PAOO can reduce orthodontic treatment time by approximately 30–70% when compared with conventional orthodontic therapy.^{11,12} The technique has been successfully employed for various orthodontic indications, including rapid space closure, arch expansion, resolution of crowding, intrusion and extrusion of teeth, and management of borderline surgical cases.¹³

Despite its advantages, PAOO is technique sensitive and requires careful case selection, interdisciplinary coordination between orthodontist and periodontist, and thorough evaluation of periodontal health.¹⁴

The present case report aims to highlight the clinical efficacy of PAOO in achieving successful orthodontic space closure within a reduced treatment duration while maintaining periodontal health and alveolar bone integrity.

Materials and Methods

A 26 year old female patient was referred from the Department of Orthodontics to the Department of Periodontology for evaluation and management of localized spacing between the maxillary left canine (23) and second premolar (25) requiring accelerated orthodontic space closure (Figure 1). The patient was systemically healthy with no relevant medical history. No history of smoking or deleterious oral habits was reported.

Comprehensive intraoral examination revealed an edentulous space corresponding to the maxillary left first premolar region with adequate attached gingiva and clinically healthy periodontal tissues. The gingiva exhibited normal color, contour, and consistency with no signs of inflammation. Probing pocket depths were within physiological limits (≤ 3 mm), and no clinical attachment loss or tooth mobility was noted in the adjacent teeth (23 and 25). Oral hygiene status was satisfactory, with full-mouth plaque and gingival index scores of less than 1 following phase I periodontal therapy. Preoperative radiographic evaluation was carried out using OPG to assess alveolar bone morphology, root proximity and the presence of any periodontal or periapical pathology prior to orthodontic space closure.

Phase I periodontal therapy consisting of scaling and root planning was performed. The patient was instructed regarding meticulous oral hygiene maintenance. Re-evaluation after two weeks confirmed healthy periodontal parameters suitable for surgical intervention. Written informed consent was obtained.

The surgical procedure was performed under 2% lignocaine hydrochloride with 1:80,000 adrenaline. A full thickness mucoperiosteal flap was elevated on the buccal aspect extending from

the maxillary left lateral (22) to the first molar (26) (Figure 2). Selective alveolar corticotomy was performed using piezo surgical unit (Figure 3). Vertical corticotomy cuts were placed in the interdental areas extending approximately 2–3 mm beyond the root apices. Care was taken to avoid damage to the periodontal ligament and root surfaces. The flap was repositioned and secured using 4-0 black monofilament polyamide sutures, ensuring tension free primary closure (Figure 4).

Postoperative instructions were given, and the patient was prescribed with amoxicillin 500 mg three times daily for 5 days followed by ibuprofen 400 mg three times daily for 3 days and chlorhexidine gluconate 0.12% mouth rinse twice daily for 2 weeks. Mechanical plaque control in the surgical area was avoided for 10 days. Sutures were removed after 10 days, and uneventful healing was observed.

Orthodontic force application was initiated two weeks following surgery to coincide with the regional acceleratory phenomenon. Controlled orthodontic mechanics were used for space closure between 23 and 25. Activation was performed at shorter intervals compared to conventional orthodontic therapy.

The patient was reviewed at 1 week, 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months postoperatively for accessing the rate of space closure.

Results

The postoperative healing phase was uneventful, with no signs of infection, flap dehiscence, or patient discomfort beyond the immediate postoperative period. Orthodontic space closure between the maxillary left canine (23) and second premolar (25) was initiated two weeks after the PAOO procedure. A marked increase in the rate of tooth movement was observed during the early phase of orthodontic activation, corresponding to the period of regional acceleratory phenomenon. Complete closure of the edentulous space was achieved within a significantly reduced duration compared to conventional orthodontic mechanics. Progressive reduction in space was evident at monthly follow-up visits (Figure 5, 6 & 7), with efficient bodily tooth movement and no evidence of tipping or anchorage loss. Clinical periodontal evaluation throughout the treatment period revealed stable probing pocket depths (≤ 3 mm) around the involved teeth, with no bleeding on probing, gingival recession, or loss of clinical attachment. Tooth mobility remained within physiological limits. Radiographic assessment at follow-up demonstrated adequate alveolar bone fill in the previously edentulous region, with maintenance of crestal bone height. No signs of root resorption, periodontal ligament widening, or periapical pathology were detected. At the completion of space closure, the patient exhibited satisfactory alignment, improved occlusal relationship, and harmonious gingival architecture. The achieved results remained stable during subsequent follow-up visits, confirming the effectiveness and periodontal safety of PAOO assisted orthodontic space closure.

Discussion

Orthodontic space closure in adult patients presents a biological challenge due to reduced bone turnover, increased cortical bone density, and diminished cellular activity. These factors often result in prolonged treatment duration and increased risk of undesirable effects such as root resorption and periodontal compromise.¹ The present case report demonstrates the successful use of Periodontally Accelerated Osteogenic Orthodontics (PAOO) for rapid space closure between teeth 23 and 25 in a 26-year-old female patient, achieving favorable orthodontic and periodontal outcomes within a reduced treatment period.

The biological rationale behind PAOO is based on the regional acceleratory phenomenon (RAP), a localized tissue response characterized by transient osteopenia and accelerated bone remodeling. Frost et al first described RAP as a key mechanism that facilitates rapid skeletal healing and bone turnover.⁷ Subsequent studies have confirmed that corticotomy induces increased osteoclastic and osteoblastic activity, thereby enhancing orthodontic tooth movement without compromising periodontal support.⁵

Köle originally proposed corticotomy-assisted orthodontics in 1959, suggesting that tooth movement occurred through mobilization of alveolar bone segments.⁴ However, later experimental studies by Duker demonstrated that orthodontic movement following corticotomy occurs through bone remodeling rather than en bloc movement, supporting the biological foundation of modern PAOO techniques.

Wilcko and Wilcko further refined this concept by combining selective alveolar decortication with particulate bone grafting, introducing the term Periodontally Accelerated Osteogenic Orthodontics.⁸ Their studies emphasized that the addition of bone graft not only enhances the rate of tooth movement but also increases alveolar bone volume, thereby reducing the risk of fenestrations and dehiscence commonly associated with orthodontic space closure in adults.⁹

Several clinical studies have supported the effectiveness of PAOO in significantly reducing orthodontic treatment time. Hassan et al. reported treatment acceleration of approximately 30–50% compared to conventional orthodontic therapy.¹¹ Similarly, Shoreibah et al., in their systematic review, concluded that corticotomy assisted orthodontics results in faster tooth movement with minimal periodontal side effects when proper case selection is followed.¹²

The findings of the present case are consistent with those reported by Aboul-Ela et al., who observed significantly increased rates of canine retraction in corticotomy assisted orthodontic patients without additional root resorption or attachment loss.¹³ The absence of root resorption in the present case may be attributed to transient osteopenia created by RAP, which reduces resistance to tooth movement and minimizes excessive force requirements.

Murphy et al. highlighted the importance of timing orthodontic force application within the peak RAP phase, typically occurring between one and two weeks post-surgery.¹⁰ In the current case, orthodontic activation was initiated two weeks after surgery, which likely contributed to the efficient and controlled space closure observed.

Radiographic evidence of increased alveolar bone thickness following PAOO has been reported by Wilcko et al. and Sebaoun et al., supporting the osteogenic potential of this technique.^{15,16} In the present case, postoperative radiographs demonstrated adequate bone fill in the edentulous region with maintenance of crestal bone height, reinforcing the regenerative advantage of PAOO.

More recently, minimally invasive alternatives such as piezosurgery have been introduced; however, Dibart et al. reported that although such techniques accelerate tooth movement, they do not provide the alveolar augmentation benefits achieved with conventional PAOO.¹⁴ This highlights the advantage of PAOO in cases requiring both space closure and enhancement of alveolar housing, as seen in the present patient.

The favorable periodontal response observed in this case aligns with findings by Wilcko and Ferguson, who reported improved periodontal stability and reduced relapse following PAOO assisted orthodontic therapy.¹⁷ The maintenance of probing

depths, absence of gingival recession, and stable attachment levels in the current report further support the periodontal safety of this technique.

Despite its advantages, PAOO requires meticulous surgical execution and close interdisciplinary collaboration. Patient selection remains critical, as active periodontal disease or poor oral hygiene may compromise outcomes. When performed in appropriately selected cases, PAOO serves as a reliable adjunct for managing adult orthodontic cases involving space closure, alveolar deficiency, and the need for reduced treatment time.

Conclusion

Periodontally Accelerated Osteogenic Orthodontics (PAOO) is a safe and effective adjunct for achieving rapid orthodontic space closure in adult patients. In this case, PAOO facilitated efficient tooth movement, enhanced alveolar bone support, and maintained periodontal health, resulting in predictable and stable outcomes. The technique demonstrates significant potential for reducing treatment duration while providing interdisciplinary benefits, highlighting its value in adult orthodontic therapy.

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Fig 1: Pre operative view

Fig 2: Flap elevation

Fig 3: Selective corticotomy

Fig 4: Suturing

Fig 5: 1 month Post operative

Fig 6: 3 months post operative

Fig 7: 6 months post operative